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Technological Volunteering as an Approach for Service Learning

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INTRODUCTION

Entities with social purposes perform an essential task in our Society. They are often obliged to work with insufficient budgets that do not allow them to develop their projects with the necessary guarantees. In particular, they require computers and support from ICT experts in order to be able to fulfil their objectives in a society as technological as ours, in which changes in technology occur at a dizzying speed. In September, 2015, the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya - BarcelonaTech launched an ICT volunteer program in the form of a pilot experience with students from the Schools of Informatics and Telecommunications. This program is an extra-curricular activity called Vol-ICT currently in its third edition and forms part of a more ambitious undertaking in which we aim to increase student retention by using Service Learning as a part of our university educational policy [1].

1 SERVICE-LEARNING

Service-Learning (SL) is an educational practice in which the learning process (content, competences and values) is combined with the detection, analysis and eventual solution of

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community needs. It is conducted by means of a project in which students are trained while working on a real project.

For Robert Sigmon [2], the SL methodology is an experimental approach in which a reciprocal benefit exists. According to the author, SL differs from other educational approaches in its intention to benefit both the provider and the recipient of the service, and to ensure that the objectives are twofold: learning and service.

The Corporation for National and Community Service [3] defines SL as a methodology where students learn by performing a useful service for the community. In this service, they must develop a work which can be integrated into the curriculum, is well structured, moves students to reflection and extends what they have learned in their studies.

SL is a meeting point between solidarity intentionality and pedagogical intentionality [4], and as such goes beyond what a simple social volunteering involves. Learning can take place as part of a voluntary service, but without necessarily expressing intentionality or without explicit mechanisms. For example, students of a Bachelor Degree in Informatics Engineering may participate as volunteers in an entity dedicated to distributing food to families in need, but this does not mean that they will be better trained as ICT Engineers, even though they will probably improve their skills as individuals. Thus, this activity may be classified according to whether it is focused on the service, on learning, or on both in an integrated manner:

- If it is focused on the service, it is fundamentally an act of solidarity. The above-mentioned case of students who collaborate with an entity that distributes food to families in need is a clear example of an activity focused on service.
- If it is focused on learning, it is an educational activity that can help raise student awareness, but without necessarily having a real impact on the community. For example, completing a Final Degree Project (FDP) that takes into account the project's sustainability is a learning task, but it is not SL.
- An activity that is focused on both learning and service constitutes authentic SL. Students develop or extend technical competencies specific to their studies, as well as professional skills such as commitment or responsibility, by means of a solidary activity that must be integrated into the curriculum and have a direct impact on the community. For example, the completion of an FDP devoted to a software that enables the (real) management of an agricultural cooperative in Morocco. This project presents students with an engineering problem involving multiple restrictions: they are required to create a complete product that is both robust and adapted to the client.

In SL, it is vital that an alliance between the university and the community is established. This alliance should serve to identify real needs that can be addressed either totally or partially by students. Furthermore, such a process should encourage students to reflect on the opportunities and risks of their profession, while at the same time entering into the emotional dimension of student engagement [5] [6] and increasing their academic commitment, all of which is intended to increase academic performance [7]. Some experiences involving SL in ICT Degrees can be found in [8].

2 THE PROJECT

In the Vol-ICT program, students carry out an ICT project in a solidary entity for a minimum of 60 hours. The project is defined by an entity with social purposes and supervised by a

member of the entity and by a professor from our university. Two ECTS credits are awarded to students for the completion of the project, one for every 30 hours of work. This number can be increased up to 6 ECTS credits if the size of the project justifies it.

2.1 Objectives of the program

The main objectives of the Vol-ICT program are as follows:

- To transform the vision that students have about society while discovering the real impact that their future profession may have on the world.
- To develop competencies that students are expected to acquire. In projects such as the Vol-ICT program, students work on 8 out of the 11 outcomes proposed by the ABET: (c) the ability to design a system, component, or process to meet desired needs within realistic constraints such as economic, environmental, social, political, ethical, health and safety, manufacturability and sustainability; (d) the ability to function as part of a multidisciplinary team; (e) the ability to identify, formulate, and solve engineering problems; (f) an understanding of professional and ethical responsibility; (g) the ability to communicate effectively; (h) the broad education necessary to understand the impact of engineering solutions in a global, economic, environmental, and societal context; (j) a knowledge of contemporary issues; and (k) the ability to use the techniques, skills, and modern engineering tools necessary for engineering practice.
- As a public university financed mainly by taxpayers, part of what we receive is returned to society through this project by helping entities with social purposes that otherwise could not afford the cost of this engineering work.

2.2 Design of the project

The UPC Vol-ICT program is managed by the Center for Development Cooperation (CCD), an office of the university devoted to organizing and supporting cooperation and volunteering initiatives undertaken by members of our community. It can also count on the participation of Technology for All (TxT) an NGO consisting of personnel and students from our university. The program works as follows.

- The selection of entities is based on a call that is published on the program's website in May. Entities must submit a project that clearly identifies the objectives to be achieved and the benefits that volunteers will receive in terms of experience and/or learning. A dialogue is established between the entities and the CCD to refine the proposals and adapt them to the objectives of the program and the expected learning outcomes.
- The projects are published in September. Students then select three projects, indicating their order of preference. A second call is issued in January to cover vacant projects or occasional volunteer dropout. In September, we also contact the professors who wish to volunteer as academic tutors for the projects.
- During the last week of September, those responsible for the program assign volunteers to projects, taking into account student preferences as well as the overall perspective of the program. A project may be assign more than one student from the same or from different schools, depending on the requirements. The assignment of professors as project tutors is also conducted according to their availability and their preferences.

- The volunteers receive training during the first week of October. A series of formative videos is made available and a face-to-face session is organized to determine the responsibilities involved in their participation. During the rest of October, specific meetings are held to launch each project. The volunteers and their academic tutors attend each meeting, as well as a member of the entity and a member of the CCD. These meetings enable us to set realistic objectives for the project and plan its implementation. From this moment on, the project progresses asynchronously according to the needs of the entity and the availability of the volunteers. The students and the entity jointly define a schedule that is compatible with the students' academic needs. During the meeting, the project may sometimes be redefined in terms of the objectives initially proposed in the call.
- On completion of the project, a survey is submitted to the entities, the students and the tutors in order to identify factors which can be improved in the following edition.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Quantitative results

In the pilot phase (2015-2016 academic year), 5 entities and 11 students participated in the Vol-ICT program to work on 8 projects. In the 2016-17 academic year, 6 entities and 11 students participated, working on 8 projects. In the current 2017-18 academic year, 12 entities and 21 students are working on 16 projects. In the first year there was only one call for volunteers in September, while in the following two editions two calls were issued, one in September and the other in January, which produced better results. We believe that this was due to the fact that this call was made at the end of January, when the students have already finished the first semester and have not yet enrolled in the second semester. In addition, the "New Year effect" seems to be very positive for the Vol-ICT program, since it appears that students start the year with a desire to undertake new projects, especially those with an altruistic purpose, which seem to be highly attractive.

With respect to the projects already carried out, most entities request the help of volunteers for three types of generic projects: (1) the design or improvement of the entity's website, (2) the design or improvement of an app aimed at fulfilling the objectives of the entity, and (3) training activities. The training activities are of two types: those aimed at improving the technological training of the entity's members (to provide a better service for their customers), and those whose purpose is to improve the technological training of the people who may benefit from the entity's activity. In the latter case, training is almost always focused on improving the employability of these beneficiaries, who belong to groups at risk of exclusion.

The call for volunteers is open to all students, in particular, those from the Informatics and the Telecommunications Schools doing both BSc and MSc degrees, although according to current UPC regulations recognition of ECTS credits can only be accorded to BSc Students.

Table 1 summarizes the number of entities, projects and volunteers that have participated in each edition of the program. It also differentiates between the number of men and women who have participated as volunteers in the program. We wish to highlight that the percentage of female volunteers exceeds by far the percentage of women enrolled in all the schools: the Informatics School (15% volunteers, 9% enrolled), and the Telecommunications School (42% volunteers, 18% enrolled).

Table 1. Summary of entities, projects and volunteers that have participated in each edition of the program

Edition	Num. of Entities	Projects Total (Web / App / Training / Others)	Volunteers			
			Total / Male / Female	By school (Total / Male / Fem.)		
				Informatics	Telecom.	Other
2015-16	5	8 (2 / 2 / 2 / 2)	11 / 6 / 5	4 / 4 / 0	7 / 2 / 5	0 / 0 / 0
2016-17	6	8 (0 / 2 / 4 / 2)	11 / 9 / 2	8 / 7 / 1	2 / 2 / 0	1 / 0 / 1
2017-18	12	16 (2 / 3 / 6 / 5)	21 / 14 / 7	8 / 6 / 2	10 / 7 / 3	3 / 1 / 2
Total	23	32 (4 / 7 / 12 / 9)	43 / 29 / 14	20 / 17 / 3	19 / 11 / 8	4 / 1 / 3

3.2 Qualitative results

In order to obtain qualitative information on the level of SL achieved by the program, and in addition to the survey conducted annually on entities, students and tutors (with the purpose of improving the next edition of the Vol-ICT), a new specific survey has been designed during the present course. It has been distributed to all entities and students who have participated in the program since its first edition. Furthermore, in order to assess the evolution of students' perspective, a distinction has been made between those who have yet to start their projects and the rest. The questions in the surveys are as follows:

Survey to students, prior to carrying out the project:

- Describe briefly the reasons that have motivated you to join the Vol-ICT program
- What do you hope to learn from the experience?
- What do you hope to contribute with your collaboration?
- What do you think the university should do to endow its activity with a greater (positive) impact on society?

Survey to students, after the completion of the project:

- Apart from the final outcome of your project, what do you think you have contributed to the entity?
- Do you think the project has improved your professional skills? Why?
- What has the realization of the project contributed to you personally? Has your way of seeing society and/or ICT changed?
- What recommendations would you give to a student starting a Vol-ICT project?

Survey to entities, after the project

- Has the project changed your point of view about ICT projects? How?
- Apart from the final outcome of project, what do you think the students have contributed to the entity?
- Do you think UPC students have undergone a personal transformation because of their participation in the project? Why?
- What recommendations would you give to an entity that wishes to propose a project for the Vol-ICT program?

To date, we have received 5 responses from entities and 13 from volunteers, a sample too small for a quantitative analysis, so we will provide a qualitative one. With respect to the entities, they indicate that a process of “mutual learning” has been achieved between students and the entity, and that the work carried out by the volunteers is something that “otherwise wouldn’t have been done due to a lack of resources”. The entities stated that “some projects can benefit from ICT more than we expected”. One entity also indicated that the volunteers “provided us with a fresh point of view and helped us to be more open-minded about ICT”. The entities consider that students “learned about social issues of which they were previously unaware”, as well as “learning to recognize the need to empower ICT tools in society”. Moreover, in one case a volunteer joined the entity’s permanent staff. Other entities have recommended their counterparts that are thinking about joining the program to “trust in the abilities of students and in their capacity to carry out projects of this nature”, as well as to “clarify the project with the help of the experts from the university” and to “define clearly the work that students are to undertake”.

With regard to the students, before joining the project they indicated that they wished to “do something useful with the knowledge I’m acquiring” and to “help people while acquiring some real experience”. In addition, they wanted to “learn to deal with people”, “learn about social entities and what impact they have on society” and “learn to work with different kinds of people”. They also expected to have an “enriching experience” and to “help others with personal growth”. They believe that the university should “help students to deal with real problems facing society” and that the experience “made us aware of our usefulness as engineers in helping people, above and beyond materialistic concerns”.

Students who completed the project considered that they had helped entities to “discover different ways of doing things”, to “adopt another mentality”, and had “provided a technical and realistic vision of what an ICT project really is and what it can become”. Basically, apart from technical issues, they had learned about “time management, sharing duties as part of a team and the need of periodic meetings”, as well as how “to communicate with non-ICT people” and how to “put myself in the shoes of someone who hasn’t had the same opportunities that I have”. For some it has been a transforming experience: “I’ve seen the real complexity of society at first hand”; “I now realize how privileged I’ve been all my life”; “I’ve seen the digital divide between different social classes”; “I’ve witnessed how young people at risk of social exclusion are able to accomplish many things when an opportunity is offered”. When it comes to giving advice to future volunteers, the opinion is unanimous: “try hard”; “don’t give up”; “work with a passion”; “do it with the desire to help or don’t do it”; “when you start, you acquire a commitment”; “make the most of the experience - the most important thing is not necessarily the project itself, but getting in touch with people”; “it is hard work, but rewarding”; “enjoy it”, and “collaborate widens the soul”.

4 DISCUSSION

Given the responses to the surveys, we believe that all our objectives have been fulfilled. We are deeply satisfied with the feedback from the entities, but especially with the way in which students have learned from the human point of view. The reports by the academics involved in the projects also indicate that the learning outcomes have been fulfilled. The number of volunteers is growing, and more are expected in future editions, and the aim is to ensure that the project remains voluntary rather than mandatory, since we believe that volunteer commitment is essential for the success of this type of project. In the light of this three-year

experience, we believe that some aspects of the program have worked really well, while others still require some improvement. In the following paragraphs we set out what we have learned from this experience.

Keeping bureaucracy to a minimum: during the design of the program, we gave great importance to formalizing documents at each step of the process, which resulted in volunteers feeling overloaded with the obligation to prepare numerous follow-up reports. Most of these reports have now been eliminated, thereby alleviating part of the process and concentrating attention on what is truly important and essential. The purpose of the monitoring system is to simply ensure that communication between the volunteer, the tutor and the entity is maintained without the impediment of unnecessary procedures.

The importance of timing: in the first edition, we did not pay enough attention to some transitory aspects, such as collecting the proposals from entities before starting the course. This led to a delay in the program to the extent that some projects were not completed until after June. The process has now been improved by adapting the program cycle to the academic calendar. In addition, the excessive elapse of time between enrolment and the actual start of the project led in some cases to demotivation. Furthermore, some volunteers have expressed a desire to participate in the program during other periods, and while this implies a more complex management of the projects, the introduction of a more flexible calendar should also be taken into account.

Specific training: we began the first edition with an initial general training in volunteering and on the relationship of ICT with society. However, the volunteer students expressed their need for specific training on the issues most closely allied with the technical work to be undertaken; for example, the creation of apps or webs.

Greater stress on the project definition: some entities may not have the technical knowledge to enable them to clearly define the requirements of the project, which sometimes gives rise to proposals that are too generic or too ambitious. Thus, more meetings were held with the entities in order to define from the outset projects based on clear and achievable objectives.

Commitment is the key: the commitment of all those involved is the only really essential factor for carrying out the tasks. In this sense, the key to success is sustaining the participants' motivation and clarifying the role of each one from the very beginning. Moreover, it is highly advisable to assign more than one student to each project in order for students to share responsibility and feel that they have more support, while the risk of a failed project due to student dropout is also reduced.

Small but safe steps: although processes may be simplified, program management still requires a wholehearted commitment in terms of human resources. While one of the goals of the program is to increase both student and teacher participation, it would be counterproductive to accelerate this process if an effective response to the expectations of the entities cannot be provided. In this regard, there is a long way to go before the program can be considered as consolidated.

5 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

It is our aim to encourage other universities to put the Service Learning methodology into practice, not only as a service to the community, but also to enrich the learning experience of

students, since these projects deepen and extend their relations with their teachers, their schools and their future profession, thus creating a sense of belonging and a greater emotional commitment to their studies, which in turn results in a better academic performance. The idea behind this paper is to share our experience in an ICT volunteer program with other universities and entities that wish to undertake a similar volunteer program, in order to encourage them to build on our successes and avoid our mistakes. We wish to thank all the lecturers and entities involved in the project, and especially our students, since they are the ones who have made these dreams a reality.

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